

Review Article

DIFFERENCES OF IRREGULAR INFLECTIONAL MORPHEMES IN ENGLISH AND ALBANIAN		Morphology Keywords: morphemes, structure of words, irregularities, mood, conjugation, etc.		
Besim Rushiti	State University of Tetova. Tetova. North Macedonia.			
<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="background-color: black; color: white; padding: 5px;">Abstract</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 10px;"> <p>Every language on the planet has its unique set of grammatical, syntactic, phonological, and morphological rules. As a result, Albanian and English have theirs as well. In this study, we attempted to demonstrate distinctions in irregular inflectional morphemes, which, as you will see, differ significantly between these two languages in this morphological area. The construction of words in these two languages differs, as does the classification of morphemes. In English, morphemes are classified into two types: derivational morphemes and inflectional morphemes. The first is concerned with morphemes that can alter the meaning of newly formed words as well as their lexical category. In the Albanian language, morphemes are classified in a different method. They are divided into two categories: root morphemes and affix morphemes. The first set of morphemes in Albanian can stand alone, i.e., they are autonomous, whereas the second group of morphemes are added to the root of the word, generating the new one.</p> </td> </tr> </table>			Abstract	<p>Every language on the planet has its unique set of grammatical, syntactic, phonological, and morphological rules. As a result, Albanian and English have theirs as well. In this study, we attempted to demonstrate distinctions in irregular inflectional morphemes, which, as you will see, differ significantly between these two languages in this morphological area. The construction of words in these two languages differs, as does the classification of morphemes. In English, morphemes are classified into two types: derivational morphemes and inflectional morphemes. The first is concerned with morphemes that can alter the meaning of newly formed words as well as their lexical category. In the Albanian language, morphemes are classified in a different method. They are divided into two categories: root morphemes and affix morphemes. The first set of morphemes in Albanian can stand alone, i.e., they are autonomous, whereas the second group of morphemes are added to the root of the word, generating the new one.</p>
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Introduction

Morphology (as defined below) is the study of the structure and form of words in a language, including inflection, derivation, and compound formation. Some features of words and their structure:

1. Some words can be divided into constituent parts while retaining their meaning.
2. Many words have inherent meaning. However, some words have meaning only when combined with others.
3. Some of the parts into which words can be divided can be used as words on their own. Others, however, cannot.
4. These word-parts that can only occur in combination must be combined correctly.
5. Languages generate new words in a systematic manner.

1. Root, Derivational, and Inflectional Morphemes

Morphemes can be classified as root, derivational, or inflectional in addition to being bound or free. A root morpheme is the fundamental form to which all other morphemes are attached. It gives the word's basic meaning. *Sawers* are derived from the morpheme (*saw*). (*-er*) is a derivational suffix that turns a verb into a noun, usually referring to the person or thing that performs the action denoted by the verb. For instance, (*paint*) + (*-er*) yields painter, one of whose definitions is "someone who paints." Separate words are not formed by inflectional morphemes. They simply modify the word in which they occur to indicate grammatical properties such as plurality, as in the (*-s*) of magazines, or past tense, as in the (*ed*) of followed. English has eight inflectional morphemes, which will be discussed further below.

The root of a word is the morpheme that remains after all derivational and inflectional morphemes have been removed. In immovability, for example, (*im-*), (*-ability*), and (*-ity*) are all derivational morphemes, and when we remove them, we are left with (move), which cannot be further divided into meaningful pieces and thus must be the word's root. We must differentiate between the root of a word and the forms to which affixes are attached. (*-able*) is attached to (move), which we've determined is the root of the word. (*im-*) is attached to moveable rather than (move) (there is no word immove), but moveable is not a root. Bases are expressions to which affixes are attached. While bases can be roots, roots are not always bases. Words are made up of "morphemes" at the most fundamental level.

Roots and affixes are the smallest units of meaning (prefixes and suffixes). The morphemes are recognized as grammatically significant or meaningful by native speakers. For example, "schoolyard" is formed by combining "school" and "yard," "makes" is formed by combining "make" with the grammatical suffix "-s" "and" unhappiness" is formed by combining "happy" with the prefix "un-" and the suffix "-ness."

Inflection occurs when a word has multiple forms but essentially the same meaning with only a grammatical difference: for example, "make" and "makes." An inflectional morpheme is "-s." In contrast, derivation creates a word with a clearly different meaning, such as "unhappy" or "happiness," both of which are derived from "happy." The morphemes "un-" and "-ness" are derivational. Normally, a dictionary would include derived words, but there is no reason to include "makes" alongside "make." The morpheme is widely accepted in modern linguistics as the smallest two-facet language unit that possesses both sound-form and meaning. Morphemes can be classified in two ways: a) from a semantic standpoint, and b) from a structural standpoint.

a) *Morphemes are classified into two types: root morphemes and non-root or affixation morphemes*

Because of the different roles they play in word structure, roots and affixes form two distinct classes of morphemes. The difference between roots and affixation morphemes is generally obvious, as in the words *helpless*, *handy*, *blackness*, *Londoner*, *refill*, and so on: the root-morphemes *help-*, *hand-*, *black-*, *London-*, *-fill* are understood as the lexical centers of the words, as the basic constituent part of a word without which the word is inconceivable. The root morpheme is the lexical nucleus of a word; it has a unique lexical meaning that no other morpheme in the language has. Furthermore, it may have all of the other types of meaning associated with morphemes¹, with the exception of part-of-speech meaning, which is not found in roots. The root-morpheme is defined as the morpheme that is shared by a group of words that make up a word-cluster, such as the morpheme *teach-in* to *teach*, *teacher*, *teaching*, *theory-in* *theory*, *theorist*, *theoretical*, and so on. Inflectional morphemes or inflections and affixation morphemes or affixes are examples of non-root morphemes. Inflections only carry grammatical meaning and are thus only relevant for the formation of word forms, whereas affixes are relevant for the formation of various types of stem — the part of a word that remains unchanged. Affixes

are divided into two types: prefixes and suffixes. A prefix comes before the root-morpheme, while a suffix comes after it. Affixes have a part-of-speech meaning as well as a generalized lexical meaning in addition to the root-morpheme meaning.

b) Morphemes are classified structurally into three types: free morphemes, bound morphemes, and semi-free (semi-bound) morphemes

A free morpheme is one that corresponds to the stem 2 or a word-form. Many root-morphemes are naturally qualified as free morphemes, such as the root-morpheme *friend* — of the noun *friendship*, which coincides with one of the forms of the noun friend. A bound morpheme can only be found as part of a word. Affixes are naturally bound morphemes because they are always part of a word. Many root-morphemes are also bound morphemes, which are always found in morphemic sequences, i.e. in combinations with “roots or affixes”. All distinct roots and pseudo-roots are morphemes. The root-morphemes are as follows: *theor-* in *theory*, *theoretical*, etc., *barbar-* in *barbarism*, *barbarian*, etc., *-ceive* in *conceive*, *perceive*, etc. Semi-bound (semi-free) morphemes such as *s1* can function in a morphemic sequence as both an affix and a free morpheme. For example, the morphemes *well* and *half* appear as free morphemes that coincide with the stem and word-form in utterances such as *sleep well*, *half an hour*," and as bound morphemes in words such as *well-known*, *half-eaten*, *half-done*." In Albanian, morphemes are classified as follows: “*Duke qene se morfemat jane njesi te kuptimshme te gjuhes edhe klasifikimi i tyre mbeshetet ne kuptimet qe shprehin*” (According to that morphemes are the smallest meaningful linguistic units, their classification is: a) *morfemat rrenjore* - root morphemes b) *morfemat ndajshitesore* - affixation morphemes¹ So there is a different classification between English and Albanian.

1.1 Problems with morphemes in English

Leonhard Lipka examines and explains the difficulties associated with identifying morphemes in English. As a result, we have the following explanation: “*Problems with morphemes*”. A single phonological can represent multiple morphemes. For example, the phoneme *-er* can represent both the comparative degree of adjectives, as in *tall-er*, and the nominal agents suffix *-er*, as in *teacher*, which is formed from the verb *teach*. A portmanteau morpheme is a morpheme that encodes more than one grammatical contrast. The same word forms are used to represent different grammatical words. This is referred to as syncretism, and it occurs as a result of neutralization when the same word is used to represent different morphological concepts. Furthermore, an approach based on morpheme-to-morpheme correspondence encounters difficulties. However, there is a problem in Albanian:

¹ Jashari, A., Kryeziu, B. (2010). Gjuhë amtare për studentët e Fakultetit të Edukimit, UP, Prishtinë.

A morpheme cannot always appear with the same phonological form, for example, the root morpheme of the verb *djeg* has the following forms through conjugation: *djeg-digj-dogja*. These are not distinct morphemes, but rather variants of the same morpheme. To identify morphemes, different word forms of a word's paradigm (for word modifying morphemes) or different words that are meaningful and formal way attached must be compared (for word-formation morphemes). To identify the present tense endings of the verbs in the first conjugation, we will compare the word-forms:

So, according to *Bahri Beci*, the explanation is as follows:

Une shkoj	Ne shkojme
Ti shkon	Ju shkoni
Ai, ajo shkon	Ata, ato shkojne ²

These word forms are distinguished by the elements *-j, -n, -jme, -ni, -jne*, which express the grammatical meanings of the tense, number, and pronoun. To identify the morphemes mentioned above, all word forms that comprise the paradigm of the given verb are compared. Albanian morphology is both synthetic and analytical. Gender, number, case, and definiteness are all inflected into nouns. Adjectives are inflected for gender and number, but not for case or definiteness. Gender: male, female, or neuter (rare). Some nouns are singularly masculine and plurally feminine. Except for some ending in *-r, -l, -ur, and -ull*, all nouns ending in a consonant are masculine. Number: both singular and plural. The plural formation is erratic.

1.2 Structure of Words

A word's constituent morphemes can be organized into a branching or hierarchical structure, also known as a tree structure. Consider the phrase "unusable." It has three morphemes:

1. Use the prefix "un-"
2. verbal stem "use"
3. suffix "-able"

What is the framework?

Is it "use" + "-able" first to make "usable," then "un-" to make "unusable"? or is it "un-" + "use" first to make "unuse," then "-able" to make "unusable"?

We prefer the first structure, which corresponds to the tree shown below, because "unuse" does not exist in English but "usable" does. The general behavior of these affixes lends support to this analysis. To create adjectives with a negative meaning, the prefix "un-" is attached to them

² Beci, B. (2005). Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe. Logos-A.

(“unhurt”, “untrue”, “unhandy”, etc.). There is also the suffix “-able,” which attaches to verbs and forms adjectives (“believable”, “fixable”, “readable”). This results in the analysis shown above. The other logically possible structure will not work because there is no way to combine the prefix “un-” directly with the verb “use.” Now consider the term “unlockable.” This is also made up of three morphemes: 1. use the prefix “un-”. 2. suffix “-able” to the verb stem “lock”. This time, however, a little thought reveals that this word has two meanings: one corresponding to the left-hand figure, meaning “not lockable,” and another corresponding to the right-hand figure, meaning “able to be unlocked.” *Un-* can, in fact, be attached to (some) verbs: *untie*, *unbutton*, *uncover*, *uncage*, *unwrap*. *Larry Horn (1988) points out that the verbs that permit prefixation within- are those that effect a change in state in some object, the form with un-denoting the undoing (!) of that change.*

This explains the two meanings of "unlockable." We can combine the suffix -able with the verb lock to create the adjective lockable, and then combine the prefix un- with lockable to create the adjective unlockable, which means "unable to be locked." Alternatively, we can combine the prefix un- with the verb lock to form the new verb unlock, and the suffix -able with unlock to form the adjective unlockable, which means "able to be unlocked." Making explicit the various possible hierarchies for a single word allows us to better understand why its meaning may be ambiguous.

Bound and Free Morphemes

Morphemes that are free: Words like *boy*, *car*, *desire*, *gentle*, and *man* can stand on their own. Morphemes that are bound: Can't stand alone - always part of a sentence. - can be found attached to free morphemes: cats: cat (bound morpheme -s free morpheme)

Unwanted: *desire*, morpheme *-un*, morphemes with *-able* suffixes

Affixes

-*Prefixes* - appear before other morphemes such as *unhappy*, *discontinue*, *rewrite*, *bicycle*, and *bipolar*.

-*Suffixes* - words that come after other morphemes -*sleeping*, *excited*, *desirable*

1.3 Roots and Stems

(BASE = a free or bound element (root morpheme or complex word) to which additional morphemes are added. Also known as a STEM)

Morphologically complex words are made up of a root and one or more morphemes (s) a lexical content's root. A morpheme that cannot be broken down into smaller parts, such as *painter*, *reread*, or *conceive*, may or may not stand alone as a word.

When we add an affix to a stem, we create a new stem and a new word.

Root: believe
 believe + capable
 un + believe + capable

Root: system
 System + atic = stem
 un+ system + atic stem
 un+ system + atic + al stem
 un+ system + atic + all + ly

Syllables and morphemes

The terms morpheme and syllable should not be used interchangeably: Many morphemes are syllable-based (i.e., contain at least one vowel)

1.4 English Inflectional Morphemes

We can see that many linguists and academic linguistics institutions have focused on inflection and morphology in general. As a result, we see the following explanation in (ENG 411B Principles of Modern Grammar): Inflection is a change that indicates the grammatical function of nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and pronouns" (e.g., noun plurals, verb tenses)

An inflectional morpheme is a word variant that is used to signal grammatical information. For instance, the suffix [-ed] indicates that a verb is in the past tense: walk-ed." There are only eight inflectional affixes in English:

1. plural noun (-s) - "He has three desserts."
2. possessive nouns (-s) - "This is Betty's dessert."
3. present tense verb (-s) - "Bill typically eats dessert."
4. past tense verb (-ed) - "He made the dessert yesterday."
5. past participle verb (-en) - "He always ate dessert."
6. verb present participle (-ing) - "He is currently eating dessert."
7. comparative adjective (-er) - "His dessert is larger than mine."
8. superlative adjective (-est) - "Her dessert is the largest."

Nouns take two inflectional morphemes, plural and possessive.(ENG 411B Principles of Modern Grammar)

Plural	-s	book + -s	books
	-es	glass + -es	glasses

Some plurals take a different morpheme:

datum > *data*

medium > *media*

ox > *oxen*

moose > *moose*

In Albanian grammar we have:

Plural	-at	Libr(i) + -at	librat
	-at	xham(i) + -at	xhamat

Possessive	-s	Barbara + -s	Barbara's
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When a singular possessive noun ends in *-s* or *-z*, the 's is retained. The 's pronunciation simply shifts from the [s] sound to the [z] sound:

Bass's maze > maze's maze

The possessive form of a plural noun ending in *-s* is pronounced in the same way as the plural form. It is spelled with a single apostrophe and no other *-s*:

The taxpayers' burden is five days' work. In Albanian grammar we have:

Possessive	E+-es	E Barbar + -es	E Barbares
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Only a few examples are provided to demonstrate the differences in grammatical forms between English and Albanian. The verb inflection system in English is relatively simple. Every verb has an infinitive form that is uninflected. Only four inflectional morphemes can be attached to the infinitive form:

Inflection	Morpheme	Function	Example	Note that...
present-tense inflections	<i>-s</i>	Used when subject is third-person singular noun or pronoun	She usually <i>sits</i> here. The house <i>stays</i> cool at night.	Verbs ending in <i>-s</i> take <i>-es</i> , e.g. <i>toss</i> à <i>tosses</i> .
past-tense inflection	<i>-ed</i>	Used to indicate past tense of a regular verb.	We <i>rowed</i> down the river. The inside of the canoe <i>got</i> pretty wet.	Irregular verbs can inflect by changing their vowel (<i>ride</i> à <i>rode</i>) or take no change (<i>cut</i> à <i>cut</i>). Some change more than a vowel (<i>go</i> à <i>went</i>).

past-participle inflection	<i>-en</i>	Used with the helping verb <i>have</i> to form the present perfect and past perfect.	I have already <i>eaten</i> . I had <i>wanted</i> a salad.	For most regular verbs, the past-participle inflection is <i>-ed</i> , just like the past-tense inflection.
present-participle inflection	<i>-ing</i>	Used with the helping verb <i>be</i> to form the present progressive.	I am <i>walking</i> to the store. You are <i>taking</i> a class.	The present-participle inflection also often occurs as a noun modifier (e.g. the <i>sleeping</i> baby; a <i>rolling</i> stone).

Adjectives in English only have two inflections: comparative and superlative.

Comparative: *-er*/taller/smarter/thicker/crazier

Superlative: *-est*/tallest/smartest/thickest/craziest

All of the example base morphemes have one or two syllables. Adjectives with more than two syllables are made comparative and superlative by adding words (*more*; *most*) rather than inflectional morphemes.

Some adverbs, like adjectives, can have comparative and superlative inflections (*-er*; *-est*):

drove farther, ran faster, and played harder

Many adverbs, however, cannot take these inflections. Take note of the awkwardness in the following phrases:

He said it slyly.

She danced the most awkwardly.

These same examples, like some adjectives, can be used to create comparatives and superlatives:

He added a sly remark.

She danced rather awkwardly.

1.5 Distinctions between derivational and inflectional morphemes

There are significant distinctions between derivational and inflectional morphemes:

<p>Derivational morphemes create “new” words. Derivational morphemes change the meanings of words. Derivational morphemes can change the word’s part of speech. Derivational suffixes always precede any inflectional suffix. Derivational suffixes have some lexical meaning. Derivational suffixes can combine with a limited subgroup of bases.</p>	<p>Inflectional morphemes show grammatical relationships. Inflectional morphemes don’t change the meanings of words. Inflectional morphemes cannot change the part of speech. Inflectional suffixes always follow any derivational suffix. Inflectional suffixes have grammatical meaning only. Inflectional suffixes can combine with nearly all members of a single part of speech.</p>
<p>Derivational morphemes can be use to create all the following words from the base friend: Nouns Friendship Friendliness Unfriendliness Adjectives friendly unfriendly friendless Verb befriend Each of these words has a different meaning than the base friend. The derivational morphemes have created a new word.</p>	<p>Inflectional morphemes can be used to create all the following words from the base fast: Friday fasts always leave me starving on Saturdays. The fast’s dates are never convenient. Wendy usually fasts when she works late. She fasted earlier this evening. Now that she is home, she is no longer fasting. She usually eats faster than I do. Bill eats the fastest. Each of these words retains the meaning of the base fast (whether as noun, verb, or adjective). The inflectional morphemes have given us grammatical information.</p>

In grammar, inflection is the transformation of a word to express various grammatical categories such as tense, mood, voice, aspect, person, number, gender, and case. Verb inflection is also known as conjugation, and noun, adjective, and pronoun inflection is known as declension. An inflection uses a prefix, suffix, or infix, or another internal modification such as a vowel change, to express one or more grammatical categories.

[1] The Albanian verb *shkoj*, which means "I go," for example, includes the suffix *-am*, which expresses person (first), number (singular), and tense (present). This suffix is used as an inflection.

In the English clause "I will lead," however, the word lead is not inflected for person, number, or tense; it is simply the bare form of lead. A word's inflected form frequently contains both a free morpheme (a unit of meaning that can stand alone as a word) and a bound morpheme

(a unit of meaning which cannot stand alone as a word). The English word *cars*, for example, is a noun that is inflected for number, specifically to express the plural; the content morpheme *car* is unbound because it can stand alone as a word, whereas the suffix *-s* is bound because it cannot stand alone as a word. Together, these two morphemes form the inflected word *cars*. Invariant words are those that are never subject to inflection; for example, the English verb *must* is an invariant item: it never takes a suffix or changes form.

2. Regular and Irregular Inflection

“When a given word class is inflectible in a given language, there are generally one or more standard patterns of inflection (the paradigms described below) that words in that class may follow.” Words that inflect in the same way are said to be regular; those that inflect differently are said to be irregular. (Expression adapted from Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia)

Many languages with verb inflection, for example, have both regular and irregular verbs. Regular verbs in English form their past tense and past participle with the ending *-[e]d*; thus, verbs such as *play*, *arrive*, and *enter* are regular. However, there are a few hundred irregular verbs that follow different patterns, such as *sing-sang-sung* and *keep-kept-kept*. Irregular verbs frequently preserve regular patterns. Other types of irregular inflected forms include irregular plurals, such as the English *mice*, *children*, and *women* (see English plural) and the Albanian *-miu-minjte*, *femije-femijet*, *grua-grate*; and irregular comparative and superlative forms of adjectives or adverbs, such as the English *better* and *best* (which correspond to the positive form *good* or *well*).

1. Irregularities can be caused by one of four factors: Euphony occurs when regular inflection results in forms that are aesthetically displeasing or difficult to pronounce (English *far farther* or *further*, in Albanian *-larg-me larg-me se largu*).
2. Principal parts—these are generally thought to have formed independently of one another, so when learning a new word, the student must memorize them. For instance, Latin *dc*, *dcere*, *dx*, *dictum* > Spanish *digo*, *decir*, *dije*, *dicho*.
3. Strong vs. weak inflection—There are two inflection systems that can exist at times, which are conventionally classified as “*strong*” and “*weak*.” English and German, for example, have weak verbs that form the past tense and past participle by adding an ending (English *jump jumped*, Albanian; *kercen-kerceu*) and strong verbs that change vowel and, in some cases, form the past participle by adding *-en* (English *swim swum*, in Albanian; *noton-notoi-notuar*).
4. Suppletion—the “*irregular*” form derives from a different root.

This phenomenon can be seen in the comparative and superlative forms of *good* in many languages. See the article on regular and irregular verbs for more information on some of the considerations that apply to regularly and irregularly inflected forms.

Grammatical conjugation and declension

- Inflections of specific word classes are referred to by two traditional grammatical terms:
- Declining a noun, pronoun, adjective, or determiner is the process of inflecting it.
- Affixes can express number, case, or gender.
- Inflecting a verb is known as conjugating it.
- Affixes can indicate tense, mood, voice, or aspect.

The declension of a noun or the conjugation of a verb is an organized list of the inflected forms of a given lexeme or root word. Below is the declension of the English pronoun *I*, which is inflected for case and number.

	singular	plural	njejës	shumës
<u>nominative</u>	I	we	Unë	Ne
<u>oblique</u>	me	us	unë	Neve
<u>possessive determiner</u>	my	our	imja	E jona
<u>possessive pronoun</u>	mine	ours	imja	Jona
<u>reflexive</u>	myself	ourselves	Vet(vetvetja)	Ne(vet ne)

In formal English, the pronoun *who* is also inflected according to case. Its declension is flawed in that it lacks a reflexive form. Here is a comparison of English and Albanian.

	singular & plural	Njejës dhe shumës
nominative	who	Kush
accusative	whom	Kujt
possessive	whose	Të kujt
reflexive	–	-

The conjugation of the verb to reach the indicative mood is shown in the table below. Suffixation is used to inflect it for person, number, and tense.

<u>Tense</u>	I	you	he, she, it	we	you	they
Present	arrive	arrive	arrives	arrive	arrive	arrive
Past	arrived	arrived	arrived	arrived	arrived	arrived
<u>Koha e foljes</u>	une	Ti	ai, ajo,	ne	ju	Ata/ato
Koha e tashme	Arritëm	arrive	arrin	arritëm	arrini	arrijnë
Koha e kaluar	arritët	arrite	arriti	arritëm	arritet	arriven

As can be seen, words in Albanian have different suffixes and are more numerous than words in English. Although not inflected for person or number, the non-finite forms arrive (bare infinitive), arrived (past participle), and arriving (gerund/present participle) can all be considered part of the conjugation of the verb to arrive. For didactic purposes, compound verb forms such as *I have arrived*, *I had arrived*, or *I will arrive* can be included in the conjugation of this verb, but

they are not overt conjugations of arrive. The covert form is derived using a formula in which the relevant inflections do not occur in the main verb pronoun + conjugated auxiliary verb + main verb in non-finite form. Furthermore, most linguists believe that the inflectional/derivational distinction is merely a sometimes-useful piece of terminology whose definitions involve a somewhat complex combination of more basic properties. As a result, we should not be surprised to encounter cases in which the distinction's application is unclear. The English suffix *-ing*, for example, has several uses that are arguably on the borderline between inflection and derivation (along with other uses that are not).

One common application of *-ing* is to indicate progressive aspect in verbs that follow forms of “*to be*”: She is leaving; he is leaving; they had inquired. This is an inflectional suffix, which is part of the system for marking tense and aspect in English verbs.

Another, related application is to create present participles of verbs that are used as adjectives: falling water; stinking mess; glowing embers. According to the rule that inflection does not change the lexical category, this is a type of morphological derivation because it converts verbs to adjectives. However, it is likely that the process involved in marking progressive aspect on verbs is the same, at least historically, because “*being in the process of doing X*”. Another common use of *-ing* to create verbal nouns is: Flying can be dangerous, and losing is excruciating. In these cases, the *-ing* forms are commonly referred to as gerunds. According to the “*changes lexical categories*” rule, this should also be a derivational affix because it converts a verb to a noun. Many people believe that grammatical context determines such cases, so that a phrase like Kim peeking around the corner surprised me is actually related to, or derived from, a tenseless form of the sentence Kim peeked around the corner. According to this viewpoint, the affix *-ing* is a type of inflection because it creates a form of the verb that is appropriate for a specific grammatical situation rather than creating a new, independent word. Thus, whether *-ing* is an inflection in this case is determined by your analysis of the syntactic relationships involved. Because of this, the distinction between inflectional and derivational affixes is merely a convenient descriptive distinction rather than a fundamental one in theory.

2.1 Nouns with irregular plurals

There are many nouns that have irregular plurals, but none that have irregular possessives:

Plural (irregular in these cases)

Possessive (always regular)

Spectrum’s mice, mouse’s, oxen ox’s

In fact, the only irregular possessives in English are his, her, my, your, and their. These exceptions, however, demonstrate the rule: these pronominal possessives function as inflections, so the possessor is always the referent of the pronoun itself, rather than some larger phrase at the end of which it happens to be at the end of.

Dr. Johanna Rubba of the English Department (Linguistics) at California Polytechnic State University — San Luis Obispo provides the following explanation: Here are some examples of irregular English inflectional morphology:

Type of irregularity	Noun plurals	Verbs: past tense	Verbs: past participle
Unusual suffix	ox en , syllabi, antenn ae		taken, seen, fallen, eaten
Change of stem* vowel	foot/feet, mouse/mice	run/ran, come/came, flee/fled, meet/met, fly/flew, stick/stuck, get/got, break/broke	swim/swum, sing/sung
Change of stem vowel with unusual suffix	brother/brethren/	feel/felt, kneel/knelt	write/written, do/done, break/broken, fly/flown
Change in base/stem form (sometimes with unusual suffix)		send/sent, bend/bent, think/ thought , teach/ taught , buy/ bought	send/sent, bend/bent, think/ thought , teach/ taught , buy/ bought
Zero-marking (no suffix, no stem change)	deer, sheep, moose, fish	hit, beat	hit, beat, come

*(BASE = a free or bound element (root morpheme or complex word) to which other morphemes are added. Also known as a STEM)

More ways inflection can be irregular:

Suppletion (instead of a suffix, the whole word changes):

be - am - are - is - was - were - been

go - went - gone

good - better - best

bad - worse - worst

some - more - most

Morphemes can also be classified as content or function morphemes, which is conceptually distinct but partially overlaps with the free-bound distinction in practice. The idea behind this distinction is that some morphemes express general referential or informational content as independently of a language's grammatical system as possible, whereas others are heavily tied to a grammatical function, expressing syntactic relationships between sentence units or obligatorily-marked categories such as number or tense. Thus, content morphemes are typically (the stems of) nouns, verbs, and adjectives: in English, content morphemes include “*throw*,” “*green*,” “*Kim*,” and “*sand*.” Because they belong to categories where arbitrary new items can be invented, content morphemes are also known as open-class morphemes. New morphemes in the following categories are constantly invented or borrowed: “*smurf*,” “*nuke*,” “*byte*,” and “*grok*.” Prepositions (“*to*,” “*by*”), articles (“*the*,” “*a*”), pronouns (“*she*,” “*his*”), and conjunctions, on the

other hand, are typically function morphemes because they either serve to connect grammatically connected elements (“*hit by a truck*,” “*Kim and Leslie*,” “*Lee saw his dog*”) or express obligatory (in a given language!) morphological features like definiteness (“*she found a table*” or “*she found the table*”). Function morphemes are also known as “*closed-class*” morphemes because they belong to categories that are essentially closed to invention or borrowing - it is extremely difficult to add a new preposition, article, or pronoun. For years, some have attempted to introduce non-gender pronouns, such as “*sie*,” into English (meaning either “*he*” or “*she*”, but not “*it*”). It is far more difficult to persuade people to use a new noun or verb.

2.2 Types of Morphemes in Albanian Language

This method of classification can be found in Albanian grammar books (Agalliu et al., 2002). So we have this description of morphemes: because morphemes are the smallest meaningful linguistic units, they are classified based on the meaning they express. As a result, there are two types of morphemes: 1. *Root morphemes* and 2. *Affix morphemes*. Because root morphemes represent the lexical core of the word, the root is equal to the core of the word. Root morphemes are classified into two types: 1. *Unconnected root morphemes* and 2. *Linked root morphemes*. The first group includes words that take a suffix to the end of the word and can stand alone without it, such as *larg-o-j*, *larg-im*, *larg-ese*, *larg-et*, *larg-esi*, and the root *larg*, which is the lexical core of all the words listed above. The root is the part of every word that must be present. There is no word that does not have a root. Root morphemes, in general, have distinct meanings from affix morphemes that are part of the same word as roots. In most cases, the meaning of the root is clear even when separated from the affixes, such as the meaning of the root *larg* to the words *larg-oj*, *larg-ese*, and *larg-as*. However, in some cases, the meaning of the root is clarified only within the word, such as the word *bath* in the words *zbath*, *mbath*. In this regard, we distinguish between free roots and linking roots. Without an affix word-formation morpheme, free roots can stand alone. For example, as previously stated, the root *qytet* of the words *qytet-eroj*, *qytet-erim*, *i qytet-eruar*, and so on. Linked roots, such as the words *-bath* verbs *mbath* and *zbath* mentioned above, cannot serve as the theme of a word because they lack any word-formation affixes, or the *-gri-*, *-kri-* roots in the words *ngrij* and *shkrij*. Only a few words in Albanian have linking roots; the majority of words have free roots. Affix morphemes are used to create new words, thus, they give the words they join a new complementary meaning, or create new grammatical meanings. *Prefixes*, *suffixes*, and *endings* are examples of affix morphemes.

Prefixes are word-formation morphemes that come before the root of the word (as in English), such as *per-hap*, *mos-besim*, and endings are morphemes that come after the root of the word, such as *fal-as*, *rrijedh-im*, and endings are morphemes that come after the suffixes and express the grammatical meaning; gender, number, tense, passive and active voice. However, in the case of conversion, the ending system (or lack thereof) that gives different parts of speech their distinctive grammatical form can be used as part of word formation. In some cases, the absence of an affix morpheme (word-forming ending or suffix) is used to express grammatical meaning.

This is due to the fact that in the form system of that part of speech, these meanings are usually expressed by endings that contain more than one phoneme. Specifically, the lack of an ending or suffix is converted to another specific meaning at this point. In these cases, the conventional approach is to use a zero ending or suffix. Thus, the noun *mal*, *mal-i*, and *mal-it* have zero endings and suffixes in these grammatical forms. Suffixes are primarily word-formation morphemes. They are distinguished not only by the position they occupy in the word structure, but also by the type of meaning they express: Endings express grammatical meaning in syntax by denoting syntax subjection of one word to another (eg. number and gender of the adjectives, number of the verb etc.) To distinguish the meaningful parts of words, i.e., to identify morphemes, different forms of a word's paradigm must be compared. To accomplish this, we will compare the following verb forms in the present tense, singular and plural (Agalliu et al., 2002): *(un) shkoj (ne) shkojm (ti) shkon (ju) shkoni (ai,ajo) shkon (ata,ato) shkojnë*. We will discuss the inflected forms of words in Albanian.

2.3 Inflection in Albanian grammar (Albanian Inflection)

Many linguists have studied the Albanian language, and it is regarded as a language with complex word formation, particularly when words take different grammar categorization, according to Jochen Trommer, who has explained some parts of the speech as follows (Jochen Trommer-Institute of Cognitive Science): Verbs are the most difficult aspect of Albanian inflection. Albanian is particularly difficult due to its extremely rich inflectional paradigms. As a result, a verb can have up to 100 different forms. Another complication is that different inflectional patterns exist for lexemes belonging to the same syntactic category: Verbs have 53 conjugational forms, whereas the assignment of plural affixes to noun stems does not follow any known systematic principle. Only the inflection of open-class elements, which is implemented by rules in our system, is discussed here. Pronominal elements exhibit interesting inflectional patterns 1, which can be captured by listing them in a full-form lexicon. According to the Albanian language book “*Gramatika e gjuhës shqipe*” by the Science Academy of Albania, we can see the following:

Adjectives

Aside from a few irregular lexemes, adjectives are divided into five inflectional classes that use the affixes *-e* (feminine gender), *-a* (feminine plural), *-e* (masculine plural), or zero in different partially overlapping distributions. Trommer (2001) demonstrated that this complex allomorphy pattern can be derived from rules based on the phonological shape and morphological constituency of adjectival stems.

Nouns

Nouns are inflected for number (singular, plural), case (nominative, dative, accusative, ablative), and other factors, as in *shtëpi-a-ve-t*, *houses-*, “*from the houses.*” While definiteness and case marking are fairly regular, i.e. predictable based on phonology, stem gender, and number, the choice of the plural suffix (*-e*, *-e*, or *-a*) is highly unpredictable.

The feminine noun *lis'* declension (tree)

Indef. Sing. Def. Sing. Def. Pl. Def. Pl.

Nom. *lis* (tree) *lisa* (trees) *lisi* (the tree) *lisat* (the trees)

Gen. *lisi lisave lisit lisave*

Dat. *Lisi lisave lisit lisave*

Accu. *Lis lisa lisiin lisat*

Abl. *Lisi lisash lisit lisave*

The declension of the feminine noun *pushë* (field)

Indef. Sing. Indef. Pl. Def. Sing. Def. Pl.

Nom. *pushë* (field) *pusha* (fields) *pusha* (the field) *pushat* (the fields)

Gen. *pushë pushave pushës pushave*

Dat. *Pushë pushave pushës pushave*

Accu. *Pushë pusha pushën pushat*

Abl. *Pushë pushave pushës pushave*

Verbs

Verbs are the most difficult aspect of Albanian inflection. There are five different moods in addition to three different tenses (present tense, aorist, and imperfect) and two different voices (*active and non-active*) (*indicative, subjunctive, optative, imperative and admirative*). Allomorphy in verbal inflection is governed in part by phonology. Thus, verbs ending in vowels form the first person aorist with *-va* (for example, *puno-va*, “*I worked*”), whereas stems ending in consonants take *-a* (for example, *hap-a*, “*I opened*”). More complicated is the division of verbs into different inflectional classes, which results in different allomorphs of affixes (e.g. for 1sg *-j* in *meso-j*, “*I learn*” and *-m* in the *-m*, “*I say*”), as well as modification of the final vowels and/or consonants of the verb stems (e.g. *vret*, “*he kills*” vs. (pl.)

The indicative mood is used for straightforward statements, declarations, and so on, such as *shkruaj* (*I write*). The admirative mood is used to express admiration, particularly when surprised or in unexpected situations. Modeling, Simulation, and Optimization - Focus on Applications is expressed using conditional and subjunctive moods. The oblique mood is used to express wishes or curses. The imperative is used to convey instructions, commands, or demands.

The tenses of verbs are *present*, *imperfect*, *future*, *past*, *present perfect*, and *past perfect*. Each mood has tenses, and each tense has six persons: three for the singular and three for the plural. Only the indicative mood contains all six tenses. Only the indicative mood contains all six tenses.

In Albanian, verbs do not have infinitives. There is a form known as *paskajore* (translated as infinitive) that performs many of the infinitive's functions. Albanian verbs also have the participle and the gerund. The participle of the verb *shkoj* (to go) is *shkuar*, the gerund is *duke shkuar*, and the infinitive is *pat shkuar*. The indicative mood conjugation of the verb *notoj* (to swim) - present, imperfect, past, and future

Imperfect Present Past Future

unë (I) notoj notoja notova do të notoj
ti (you) noton notoje notove do të notosh
ai, ajo (he, she) noton notonte notoi do të notojë
ne (we) notojmë notonim notuam do të notojmë
ju (you) notoni notonit notuat do të notoni
ata (they) notojnë notonin notuan do të notojnë

The indicative mood conjugation of the verb *notoj* (to swim) - the perfect tenses Past Perfect Present Perfect

unë (I) kam notuar kisha notuar
ti (you) ke notuar kishe notuar
ai, ajo (he, she) ka notuar kishte notuar
ne (we) kemi notuar kishim notuar
ju (you) keni notuar kishit notuar
ata (they) kanë notuar kishin notuar

These are just a few of the many grammatical forms of verbs in Albanian that take in many grammatical categories, and we used them as examples to compare word forms in their internal structure with words in English, and it is clear that Albanian language is very rich in word forms through different grammatical categories. It can also be seen that words in Albanian undergo a variety of phonetic changes on the inside.

3. Conclusion

In this study, we can clearly see the differences between the morphemes, first in their classification the types of morphemes their function, the forms they take through different grammatical categories, phonetic changes within the words criteria that are taken for the morpheme classification, and we can see that classification of morphemes to both languages are different.

When we compare the number of new forms that take words undergoing many grammatical categories, we see that the Albanian language is richer in terms of the changes the words are taken, including phonetically changes within the words, changes in their structure taking into account the morphemes they take and change, various word formation and their meaning, transferring from one class of parts of speech to another. If we look at the verbs and their forms, we can see how many different morphemes they have. The verb forms in tenses, passive and active voice, mood, number, and gender are all shown here. In every grammatical category, we can see gender rules, singular and plural for both genders, and adjectives that differentiate based on gender. We can see changes in verb conjugation, changes in pronouns, including gender and number. Another instance of word change in the Albanian language is declension. The main topic of this study was irregular inflectional morphemes, and we saw that there are only a few of them in English, while this definition is not mentioned at all in Albanian. Thus, comparing the morphology of these two languages is unavoidable.

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